

BILCC: A new resource for exploring L2 Chinese pragmatic competence

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This paper examines the validity of a new resource for the study of the pragmatic competence in L2 Chinese: The Bimodal Italian Learner Corpus of L2 Chinese (BILCC; Iurato, in press A).

Given the lack of data from Italian learners in existing L2 Chinese corpora (Iurato 2022a; 2022b), the increasing number of L2 Chinese learners in Italy (Conti & Romagnoli, 2021), and the scarcity of pragmatically tagged learner corpora in LCR (Callies, 2015), BILCC was designed to fill these gaps by providing data from Italian learners for the study of the pragmatic knowledge of Chinese *shì...de* clefts.

Eight theoretically motivated tasks (Sinclair, 2005; Tracy-Ventura & Myles, 2015; Bell & Payant, 2021; Lozano, 2021) were designed to collect written and oral data: two discourse completion tasks and two picture-based narratives (written tasks); one closed role-play, two open role-plays, and one picture description (oral tasks). The tasks were completed by 103 Italian learners, grouped into beginner, intermediate, and advanced levels according to their HSK Chinese language proficiency test scores. 35 L1 Chinese speakers also completed the tasks for comparison purposes.

Considering that Chinese clefts have corrective contrastive and non-contrastive functions (Iurato, in press B), BILCC distinguishes two different pragmatic functions for annotating the corpus data at the pragmatic level: intensification and corrective contrast. Intensification refers to non-contrastive clefts where the focus has the original function of highlighting a piece of information (Garassino, 2016; Korzen, 2014). Contrast refers to contrastive clefts with a corrective contrastive focus (Hartmann & Veenstra, 2013).

The study will address the following research questions:

RQ1: Does the variability of the tasks used to compile BILCC allow us to observe differences in the linguistic competence of Italian learners at different proficiency levels in the use of Chinese clefts?

RQ2: Are there differences in the use of the construction between learners and native speakers?

Preliminary results show that *shì...de* clefts are used more by intermediate and advanced learners. Learners use more contrastive than non-contrastive clefts in both oral and written

production, whereas native speakers tend to use clefts non-contrastively. Learners' poor L2 pragmatic competence is arguably caused by the challenges posed by the syntax-pragmatic interface, since the acquisition of information structures such as *shì...de* clefts requires learners' interlanguage to implement a cross-domain interaction between the syntactic module and the pragmatic system, as argued by the Interface Hypothesis (Sorace & Serratrice, 2009).

References

- Bell, P. & Payant, C. (2021). Designing learner corpora. Collection, transcription, and annotation. In N. Tracy-Ventura and M. Paquot (eds), *The Routledge Handbook of Second Language Acquisition and Corpora* (pp. 53-67). London-New York: Routledge.
- Callies, M. (2015). Learner corpus methodology. In S. Granger, G. Gilquin, F. Meunier (eds), *The Cambridge Handbook of Learner Corpus Research* (pp. 35-55). Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Garassino, D. (2016). Using cleft sentences in Italian and English. A multifactorial analysis. In A.-M. De Cesare & D. Garassino (eds), *Current issues in Italian, Romance and Germanic non-canonical word orders. Syntax-information structure-discourse organization* (pp. 181-204). Bern, Peter Lang.
- Hartmann, K. & Veenstra, T. (2013). Introduction. In K. Hartmann & T. Veenstra (eds), *Cleft structures* (pp. 1-32). Amsterdam: John Benjamins.
- Iurato, A. (2022a). Learner corpus research meets Chinese as a second language acquisition: Achievements and challenges. *Annali di Ca' Foscari. Serie Orientale*, 58(1): 709-742.
- Iurato, A. (2022b). Analyzing Chinese learner corpus research and Chinese learner corpora: Main features, critical issues and future pathways. *Kervan*. 26(1): 531-562.
- Iurato, A. (in press A). Designing and compiling the written sub-corpus of the Bimodal Italian Learner Corpus of Chinese (BILCC): Methodological issues. In S. Zuccheri (ed.), *Studies on Chinese Language and Linguistics in Italy* (pp. 197-228). Bologna: Bologna University Press.
- Iurato, A. (in press B). Exploring the pragmalinguistic knowledge of the 是 *shì...de* cleft construction in L1 Italian learners' L2 Chinese: Triangulation of corpus and experimental data. In I. Kecskes & H. Zhang (eds), *Chinese as a Second Language from Different Angles*. Leiden: Brill.
- Korzen, I. (2014). Cleft sentences. Italian-Danish in contrast. In A.-M. De Cesare (ed.), *Frequency, Forms and Functions of Cleft Constructions in Romance and Germanic: Contrastive, Corpus-Based Studies* (pp. 217-275). Berlin, De Gruyter.
- Lozano, C. (2021). CEDEL 2: Design, compilation, and web interface of an online corpus of L2 Spanish acquisition research. *Second Language Research*, 1-19. DOI: 10.1177/02676583211050522.
- Romagnoli, C. & Conti, S. (eds) (2021) *La Lingua Cinese in Italia. Studi su Didattica e Acquisizione*. Roma: Roma Tre Press.
- Sinclair, J. (2005). Corpus and text – basic principles. In M. Wynne (ed.), *Developing linguistic corpora: A guide to good practice* (pp. 1-16). Oxford: Oxbow Book Company.
- Sorace, A. & Serratrice, L. (2009). Internal and external interfaces in bilingual language development: Beyond structural overlap. *International Journal of Bilingualism*, 13(2): 195-210.

Tracy-Ventura, N. & Myles, F. (2015). The importance of task variability in the design of learner corpora for SLA research. *International Journal of Learner Corpus Research*, 1(1): 58-95.
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